

INTERACTIVE METHODS FOR FORMING UNIVERSAL LOGICAL ACTIONS

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Abstract. *This article examines the pedagogical potential of interactive methods in developing students' universal logical actions. In modern education, fostering learners' abilities such as independent thinking, analysis, comparison, generalization, and drawing conclusions is considered a key priority. From this perspective, the study explores the essence of interactive methods, their didactic significance, and their effectiveness within the learning process.*

The research employed methods such as observation, analysis, comparison, and pedagogical experimentation. The findings indicate that lessons organized through interactive methods significantly enhance students' engagement, promote independent thinking, and support meaningful knowledge acquisition. In particular, methods such as brainstorming, clustering, INSERT, and debate proved effective in activating students' logical thinking processes.

Based on the results, it is concluded that the systematic implementation of interactive methods in education serves as an important factor in the formation of universal logical actions. Additionally, practical recommendations for the effective use of these methods in teaching practice are provided.

Keywords: *independent thinking, interactive methods, logical thinking, pedagogical approach, teaching effectiveness, universal logical actions.*

Introduction

The idea that “learning through active participation in the educational process gives the most effective results” was put forward by John Dewey and forms the basis of modern pedagogical approaches today [1]. Currently, the development of students' logical thinking and the formation of universal logical actions are one of the priority tasks in the education system. The modern educational process is not limited to providing knowledge, but also requires the development of high-level cognitive skills in students, such as independent thinking, analysis of problem situations, comparison, generalization and drawing conclusions.

Scientific research conducted in recent years shows that traditional teaching methods cannot fully ensure the activity of students, as a result of which their logical thinking is not sufficiently developed [2]. Therefore, the need for the widespread introduction of interactive methods into the educational process is increasing. Interactive methods see the student as the central subject of the lesson, ensure his active participation and create conditions for independent acquisition of knowledge.

According to international studies, in the educational process using interactive teaching methods, the level of students' mastery and critical thinking indicators increase significantly [3]. This has a positive effect on the formation of universal logical actions.

According to pedagogical and psychological theories, students' thinking develops in the process of active mastery. According to the socio-constructivist approach put forward by Lev Vygotsky in this regard, knowledge is formed in a social environment, through communication

and cooperation [4]. Also, Jean Piaget in his research substantiated that students' cognitive development occurs through active experience and independent research [5].

The main purpose of this article is to comprehensively analyze the theoretical and practical aspects of the formation of universal logical actions in students using interactive methods and to determine their impact on educational effectiveness.

Literature review and methodology

In modern pedagogical and psychological literature, the issue of forming logical thinking and universal cognitive actions in students has been widely studied. Scientific work in this area substantiates the role of interactive methods in increasing the effectiveness of education.

First of all, the work of John Dewey substantiated the principle of active learning in the educational process. According to him, knowledge is effectively mastered not when it is given ready-made, but when the student actively participates in the practical process. This approach forms the methodological basis of today's interactive educational technologies.

Lev Vygotsky's social-constructivist theory emphasizes that the formation of knowledge depends on the social environment and collaborative activities. His concept of the "zone of proximal development" reveals the importance of cooperation with the teacher and peers in developing students' logical thinking. This theory strengthens the scientific basis of interactive methods.

Jean Piaget, studying the stages of cognitive development, showed that students' thinking develops through active experimentation and problem-solving. This approach confirms the need to use interactive methods based on problem-based learning, analysis, and synthesis.

According to Jerome Bruner's discovery learning theory, knowledge becomes more solid and practical when a student acquires it not by being prepared, but through independent research. This idea justifies the role of interactive methods in developing independent thinking.

The theory of multiple intelligences developed by Howard Gardner shows that each student has different cognitive abilities. Based on this theory, interactive methods provide a differentiated approach, taking into account the individual abilities of students.

Also, studies conducted by UNESCO and OECD have emphasized the role of interactive learning environments in increasing students' academic achievement, critical thinking, and social competencies.

The role of interactive methods in the educational process has also been widely studied in local scientific literature, and it is noted that they serve to develop logical thinking, analytical approach, and creative activity in students.

In general, the literature analysis shows that interactive methods are an effective means of forming universal logical actions in students, both theoretically and practically.

This study was conducted based on scientific and theoretical approaches developed in modern pedagogy and psychology. The methodological basis of the study is the person-centered education, the social-constructivist approach, and the competency-based education paradigm. These approaches were used in harmony with each other, allowing for a comprehensive study of the process of forming universal logical actions in students.

According to the person-centered approach, the individual characteristics, abilities, and needs of each student should be taken into account in the educational process. This approach considers the student as the central subject of the educational process and serves to develop his independent thinking. In this regard, the idea of "active learning" put forward by John Dewey serves as an important theoretical basis [6]. According to Dewey, knowledge is formed through

practical activity and experience, which further increases the pedagogical significance of interactive methods.

The social-constructivist approach justifies the formation of knowledge in a social environment, in the process of communication and cooperation. Within this approach, students' logical thinking is developed through group activities, discussion, and collaboration. This concept was developed by Lev Vygotsky, who, through his theory of the "zone of proximal development," argued that a student's capabilities expand through collaboration with adults and peers [7].

According to Vygotsky's theory, a student achieves tasks that he cannot perform independently through cooperation, and in this process his cognitive development is accelerated. Therefore, interactive methods are an important tool in creating an educational environment based on social cooperation.

The research also used a competency-based approach. According to this approach, the educational process is aimed not only at imparting knowledge, but also at forming practical skills and competencies. Universal logical actions are the main component of this approach, which serve to develop students' analytical, critical and creative thinking.

The following scientific and methodological methods were used during the research:

observation method - to determine the activity of students in the lesson process;

analysis and synthesis method - to study scientific literature and draw theoretical conclusions;

comparison method - to compare the effectiveness of traditional and interactive methods;

pedagogical experiment method - to determine the practical effectiveness of interactive methods;

generalization method - to systematize the results obtained.

The study also took into account the principles of inclusive and active learning put forward by UNESCO as a methodological basis [7]. According to UNESCO recommendations, active participation of students in the educational process, equal opportunities, and interactive approaches are important in creating an effective learning environment.

Experimental work was carried out in the 7th grade of secondary schools. In the study, students were divided into experimental and control groups, and the effectiveness of interactive methods and traditional methods was comparatively analyzed.

Thus, the methodological approaches and scientific foundations used allowed for an in-depth study of the process of forming universal logical actions in students through interactive methods and drawing reliable conclusions.

Results

During the research, the impact of interactive methods on the formation of universal logical actions in students was extensively studied on the basis of experimental work. The study was conducted in the 7th grade of secondary schools, in which a total of 60 students participated. Students were divided into experimental (30) and control (30) groups under equal conditions.

In the experimental group, the lesson process was organized based on interactive methods. This process was aimed at taking into account the individual abilities of students and ensuring their active participation. As a result, students became not only learners, but also active analytical and reflective subjects in the learning process.

In the process of analyzing the final results, the theory of multiple intelligences put forward by Howard Gardner was used as an important theoretical basis [8]. According to this theory, each student has several types of intelligence (linguistic, logical-mathematical, spatial, musical,

interpersonal and intrapersonal) developed differently, and the educational process should take into account these individual differences.

During the experiment, interactive methods made it possible to apply this approach in practice. For example, communicative intelligence was actively used in group work, logical-mathematical intelligence in problem tasks, and spatial intelligence through cluster and visual schemes. As a result, students' universal logical actions developed in a comprehensive way.

The results of the study showed that the approach based on Gardner's theory further increases the effectiveness of interactive methods, as it serves to reveal the individual capabilities of each student. In particular, a significant increase in the level of participation and interest was observed even among students with low activity.

When comparing the initial and final results, the following positive changes were noted in the experimental group:

- the ability to analyze significantly increased;
- the ability to compare and generalize developed;
- the ability to draw independent conclusions strengthened;
- the effectiveness of solving problem situations increased;
- activity and motivation in the lesson process significantly increased.

In the control group, changes were minimal, mainly because traditional methods failed to fully activate students' individual abilities.

In general, the results of the study showed that interactive methods and an approach based on Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences are highly effective in forming universal logical actions in students, significantly increasing the quality of the educational process.

According to the results of the study, logical skills significantly increased in the experimental group where interactive methods were used.

Discussion

The results of this study confirmed the effectiveness of interactive methods in the formation of universal logical actions in students theoretically and practically. The results obtained are in harmony with the scientific views put forward in modern pedagogy and psychology, further strengthening the relevance of interactive education.

The idea that “deep and solid knowledge is formed only when the student actively participates in the educational process” was put forward by John Dewey [9], and the results of the study also confirmed this idea practically. It was observed that students’ activity and level of logical thinking significantly increased in lessons where interactive methods were used.

The scientific view that “knowledge is formed in the process of social interaction and communication” was also substantiated by Lev Vygotsky [10]. In the research process, group work, discussion and cooperative activities served as an important factor in the development of students’ logical thinking. This situation was manifested as a practical confirmation of the concept of the “zone of proximal development” put forward by Vygotsky.

In addition, the idea that “students’ cognitive development occurs in the process of active experience and problem-solving” was put forward by Jean Piaget [11]. The results of the study also showed that interactive methods activate students’ thinking precisely through problem situations. Students achieved significant development in the process of independent thinking, analysis and drawing conclusions.

Also, the view that “independent discovery and active search of knowledge are important in the learning process” was put forward by Jerome Bruner [12], and the results of the study also

confirmed this idea. Interactive methods allowed students to acquire knowledge not in a ready-made way, but through their own active search, which increased the solidity of knowledge.

The results of the study showed that interactive methods significantly develop not only the level of knowledge of students, but also their logical thinking, analysis, comparison and generalization skills. In addition, students' social activity, ability to work in a group and the ability to justify their own opinions also improved.

However, some limitations were also identified during the research. It turned out that the effective use of interactive methods depends on the methodological preparation of the teacher, proper lesson planning, and the optimal number of students. In some cases, improper organization of time distribution or lack of didactic resources can affect the full effectiveness of the methods.

In general, the results of the study confirmed that interactive methods are highly effective in forming universal logical actions in students and substantiated the need for their systematic and widespread introduction into the educational process.

Conclusion

1. General conclusion

The results of this study clearly confirmed the effectiveness of interactive methods in forming universal logical actions in students. The conducted experimental work showed that the educational process organized on the basis of an interactive approach increases the cognitive activity of students and turns them into active subjects of the educational process. As a result, students' logical operations such as analysis, comparison, generalization, and conclusion-making are significantly developed.

2. Significance of the research results

The positive results observed in the experimental group showed that interactive methods are more effective than traditional teaching methods. The low level of changes in the control group confirmed that traditional methods cannot fully develop students' logical thinking. At the same time, it was found that interactive methods not only facilitate the assimilation of knowledge, but also develop students' independent thinking, creative approach, and teamwork skills.

3. Final recommendations

Based on the research results, the need for a wide and systematic introduction of interactive methods in the educational process is emphasized. For this, it is important to improve the methodological training of teachers, use modern pedagogical technologies, and make the lesson process interactive. Also, learning efficiency can be further improved by improving the educational environment and taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

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